

MultiXscale

Technical report on performance-portable electrostatics

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	Contributors:	Godehard Sutmann (FZJ)
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¹r.bartolomeu@fz-juelich.de

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Executive Summary

With the fast changing High Performance Computing (HPC) landscape, the need of performance portable implementations has grown significantly in the past years. Among the TOP 50 machines on the [TOP500](#) list, only 10% do not rely on Graphical Processing Unit (GPU)s as accelerators for its performance. Moreover, accelerators from multiple vendors hold the top spots on the list. The same picture is also present on European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) and Gauss Supercomputing Centre (GCS) machines. Both have supercomputers with AMD and NVIDIA GPUs of different generations, architectures, and compute capabilities.

This striking reality poses a growing demand for performance portability of scientific codes, libraries, and applications. For many domain applications, the efficient use of CPUs alone is not sufficient to extract the available performance and energy efficiency available on modern architectures. As an example, the worlds most energy efficient supercomputer JEDI (EuroHPC/FZJ) is based on Nvidia's Grace-Hopper Superchip, which combines CPU and GPU. In this system the GPUs can be programmed using Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA), however doing so the code would not be able to run on other vendor's platforms.

Achieving performance portability can be accomplished by pairing devices and leveraging offloading of compute kernels through frameworks such as OpenMP, OpenACC, Kokkos, or Raja. Our preliminary research on a performance portable Ewald summation method enlightens the necessity for further comparison between different software frameworks to determine the most effective approach. Therefore, a performance portability study was conducted using the N-body problem as a test case to evaluate the efficacy of various programming models across major GPU vendors. This study aimed to evaluate the relative strengths and weaknesses of each model, providing valuable insights into the optimal approach for achieving performance portability across diverse hardware architectures.

For electrostatic computations based on variants of the Ewald summation method, which are often one of the most compute intense and time consuming steps of Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations, not only portability is desired but also modularity. Task division can be achieved by separating the short-range and long-range contributions to the electrostatic potential and forces. Since the real-space and Fourier k-space parts have different performance characteristics, a multi-domain partitioning approach can be applied in conjunction with adjusting relevant Ewald method parameters. This allows for a balanced computational load across independently running partitions. To achieve optimal load balancing between the real-space and k-space partitions, it is essential to optimize operations performed on both parts as well as the amount of compute resources allocated to each task.

In this deliverable, we present advances, implementation details, rationale, and benchmarks related to the aforementioned methods. The outcomes of the performance portability study, as well as the previously reported FFT benchmark, serve as foundation for the design choices included in the development of P3M method and the portable electrostatic solver library.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable aims at providing information on the implementation of a performance portable electrostatics solver and the integration of the ALL load balancing library into LAMMPS.

This report contains elements relevant to Task 2.3 - *Performance-portable electrostatics solvers and load-balancing* lead by Forschungszentrum Jülich.

1.2 Target audience

This report is intended for readers with technical expertise in HPC or in the use of multi scale particle based simulation software. While potential users might be interested into the details reported here, the main purpose is to report on the results and implementations that might be more of interest for scientific software developers willing to interface their code to the portable electrostatic solver library.

1.3 Report outline

This deliverable reports on all relevant topics with respect to Task 2.3, led by Forschungszentrum Jülich.

The deliverable is divided into four parts:

- **Performance Portability:** in this section we present the up-to-date status on the performance portability of the most commonly used C++ portable programming models. During the course of Task 2.3 a study was conducted to access the usability and performance of such models. As outcome, an updated status on the portability was reported. Practical experience in the usage as well as a deeper understanding of the implementation details of each model was acquired. This section contributed to the choice of the programming model used for the implementations of electrostatic solvers.
- **Theoretical foundations of Ewald sum and P3M methods:** in this section we present the formulation of the basic Ewald sum, which is the original method to compute the electrostatic energy of an atomistic system under periodic boundary conditions. The accelerated version, P3M, makes use of the Fast Fourier transform, evaluated on a regular mesh, carrying the mapped particle charges. Cardinal B-Splines are applied to map charges to the mesh and to retrieve potential energies and forces back to the particles. While being able to control the approximation error, the P3M method is reducing the computational complexity from $\mathcal{O}(N^{3/2})$ down to $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$, where N is the number of particles in the system.
- **Electrostatic Solver Library:** in this section we discuss the design and implementation of the performance portable and scalable library approach for electrostatic solvers. In the present project we focus on the Ewald summation as a benchmark implementation and the P3M as an optimized implementation for production runs on modern HPC systems. Performance portability has been considered for both the real and reciprocal space part of the method. Proper parameter choice for error control and aspects of different scalability of real and reciprocal space parts are discussed and considered in the design of the library. First benchmarks on different architectures are shown and properties of scalability are discussed in terms of different tasks in the method.
- **Load Balancing:** with the intent to benchmark the load balancing methods available in the A Load balancing Library (ALL) within using our key application codes. We have integrated ALL to LAMMPS through an interface that provide users the capability of using extended *fix* commands. In the context of this deliverable we present benchmarks comparing LAMMPS performance using A100 and GH200 GPUs.

1.4 Partner contributions

JSC contributed as planned to the work in this deliverable which is intended to be contribute to realisation of other tasks in the project.

2 Performance Portability

The ongoing development of new GPUs from various vendors requires continuous monitoring of portable frameworks' performance and versatility. A primary concern is whether a portable framework is available and functional on a given architecture.

While the concept of portability between different platforms is straightforward, defining and measuring performance portability is more complex. Successful program execution is a clear indicator of portability, but evaluating performance portability requires a more nuanced approach.

A common method for assessing the performance and capabilities of portable programming models involves using mini-apps or full applications to gather relevant data [1, 2]. This can be achieved by porting a single application to various performance-portable programming models [3–6] or by porting multiple mini-apps to one performance-portable programming model and comparing the results to other available versions [7]. In our study, we focus on the N-body problem [8].

The N-body problem is a significant problem class and has been identified as one of the seven original dwarfs in Ref. [9], each representing a compelling use case with its own challenges. Many scientific fields require computing forces between pairs of interacting particles, such as gravitational forces in astrophysics, electrostatic forces in charged systems, and van der Waals forces for modeling atomic systems.

The gravitational potential between particles is given by:

$$U(d_{ij}) = -G \frac{m_i m_j}{d_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

where $G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^2}$ is the gravitational constant, $d_{ij} = |\mathbf{r}_{ij}|$ is the distance between particles i and j , $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$, and m_i and m_j are the masses of the respective particles.

Given a potential $U(d_{ij})$, the force \mathbf{f}_{ij} between particles i and j is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{ij} = -\nabla U(d_{ij}) = -G \frac{m_i m_j}{d_{ij}^3} \mathbf{r}_{ij}. \quad (2)$$

The total force acting on particle i is then given by the sum over all other particles

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \sum_{j \neq i} \mathbf{F}_{ij}. \quad (3)$$

To obtain the trajectory of each particle, Newton's equations of motion

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \mathbf{v}_i \quad , \quad \dot{\mathbf{v}}_i = \mathbf{a}_i = \frac{\mathbf{F}_i}{m_i}, \quad (4)$$

are integrated, where the dot-notation represents the time derivative, \mathbf{a}_i is the acceleration, and m_i is the mass of particle i .

The gravitational N-body problem (the 4th dwarf in Ref. [9]) is a representative of an algorithmic method that includes long-range interactions in open-boundaries and involves summation over all particle pairs in the system to compute the forces on each particle, resulting in a natural computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. To avoid this quadratic complexity, more efficient methods like the Barnes-Hut tree method or the fast multipole method (FMM) can be used, reducing the complexity to $\mathcal{O}(N \log(N))$ or $\mathcal{O}(N)$. However, since these methods have a high level of complexity and their performance strongly depends on the implementation and optimization, we focus here on a simple implementation based on the all-pairs computation of energies and forces, which isolates the performance outcome from algorithmic issues.

To evaluate the utilization of the hardware architectures in our benchmarks, we compared the throughput of particle-particle computations, where the number of interactions scales as N^2 . The study used the N-body problem as a test from compute intense algorithm that is present in many MD software. An illustration of the program workflow is presented in Figure 1.

In order to evaluate the performance portability of different programming models, the discussed algorithm was implemented in eleven variations. The C++ frameworks considered were: Kokkos [10], OpenMP, OpenACC, SYCL, HIP, CUDA, and pSTL. The implementations were tested on four platforms. An overview of the tested platforms is presented in Table 1.

For details about platform specifications, compilers, implementations, and optimizations, readers may refer to [8].

Figure 1: Sequence of operations and program flow within the N-body problem. The main phase of the program is repeated for N_t iterations, each computing a discrete time step of size dt . P.I.: particle initialization; F.C.: force computation; $\Delta\vec{r}$: propagation of positions in Velocity Verlet; $\Delta\vec{v}$: propagation of half step velocities in Velocity Verlet integrator.

Architecture	OpenMP	pSTL	Kokkos	CUDA	HIP	SYCL	OpenACC
Nvidia A100	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Nvidia GH200	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
AMD MI250	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Intel GPU Max 1100	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗

Table 1: Overview of implementations on investigated architectures. ✓ indicates that benchmarks were performed. ✗ indicates that the implementation was not supported on that architecture at the time of the benchmark.

As shown in Figure 2, more powerful GPUs require larger system sizes to saturate the processor, indicated by the flattening of the lines in the plots.

The results show that variants using shared memory generally perform better than those without it, particularly on the GH200. However, there are some exceptions that require further investigation. Notably, CUDA on the GH200 with shared memory achieved the best results, while SYCL outperformed HIP on the MI250. In contrast, OpenMP and pSTL outperformed SYCL on the Intel platform. Furthermore, OpenACC, OpenMP, and pSTL surprisingly achieved higher performance on the A100 card compared to CUDA with shared memory. These findings align with a study by [11], which found that SYCL’s software stack improvements led to outperforming native programming models on compute-bound kernels. These results are also presented numerically in Figure 2 for discussion:

Using the mean application efficiency $\bar{\%}$ (see Equation 5), it can be seen that the models designed to be portable perform better than those targeted at specific platforms (HIP, CUDA). Although this is to be expected, it is noteworthy that pSTL and SYCL (using shared memory) show the best portability quality. Kokkos shows comparatively lower performance on the AMD and Intel platforms. Regarding AMD, our result differs from recent studies, where Kokkos showed excellent performance on AMD-based systems [2, 12]. This may be due to the variant chosen for its performance on the GH200.

$$\bar{\%} = \frac{\frac{\%_{A100} + \%_{GH200}}{2} + \%_{MI250} + \%_{Max1100}}{3}. \quad (5)$$

The respective results for $\bar{\Phi}$ (Table 2) show little deviation from the results for $\bar{\%}$ for the portable programming model, but make it clear that CUDA, HIP, and OpenACC are not portable since they are not applicable (NA) per definition for programming models that cannot be executed on one or more of the investigated architectures. The deviation in the percentages for the portable programming models comes from the different ways of averaging (see. Equation 5).

For a more detailed analysis of performance portability the number of taken measurements as well as the number of targeted platforms would need to be increased. Despite this, the performed analysis on the presented data already indicates that using an optimized version of a code on a given architecture (in this case the GH200) might not be optimally suited for other architectures, but still performs satisfactory well on the most modern system from all major HPC GPU vendors.

Our results show that OpenMP, pSTL, and SYCL are well suited for portable implementations of the N-body problem across various GPU vendors, while Kokkos showed slightly reduced performance on the non-Nvidia platforms. Kokkos

Figure 2: Interactions per second vs number of particles N on the investigated architectures by the different implementations. Note the different scale of the y-axis for GH200 (b). We do not include the results for OpenACC on the MI 250 since they are about a factor of 100 lower than those from the other programming models and nearly independent of system size.

might show better performance, when using algorithms more dependent on complex memory access patterns, e.g., short-range interactions, as in the case for Ewald Sum and the Particle-Particle Particle-Mesh algorithms.

	A100		GH200		MI250		GPU Max 1100		$\bar{\%}$	$\bar{\Phi}$
	$[\frac{\text{GInt}}{\text{s}}]$	%	$[\frac{\text{GInt}}{\text{s}}]$	%	$[\frac{\text{GInt}}{\text{s}}]$	%	$[\frac{\text{GInt}}{\text{s}}]$	%		
CUDA	165	93	369	87					30	NA
CUDA (s)	172	97	423	100					33	NA
HIP	164	92	370	87	182	98			63	NA
HIP (s)	169	95	398	94	179	97			64	NA
Kokkos	166	94	366	87	145	78	130	71	80	83
OpenACC	176	99	371	88	1.5	1			32	NA
OpenMP	177	100	371	88	142	78	184	100	91	92
pSTL	174	98	365	86	182	98	181	98	96	95
SYCL	159	90	370	87	176	95	171	93	92	91
SYCL (nd)	158	89	368	87	185	100	173	94	94	93
SYCL (s)	167	94	411	97	185	100	175	95	<u>97</u>	<u>97</u>

Table 2: Fastest measured performance data across different system sizes, measured in Giga-interactions per second ($\frac{\text{GInt}}{\text{s}}$) on each platform for each programming model. The fastest overall measured performance is used as reference value for the application efficiency (%) and is indicated in bold. $\bar{\%}$ (cmp. Eq. 5) is the weighted mean of % over all architectures, assuming % = 0, when benchmarks could not be performed. The underlined result is the best achieved value for $\bar{\%}$. (s) indicates variants using shared memory, while (nd) indicates the SYCL variant using nd-ranges. The last column shows the performance portability metric $\bar{\Phi}$.

3 Electrostatics Methods and Implementation Considerations

Ewald techniques are able to compute the long range interactions contributing to electrostatic forces for many systems. Within the scope of this work, we are particularly interested in methods that concern Coulomb point charges, as they are present in multi-scale particle simulations.

Previous descriptions and implementations of such methods can be found in the literature [13]. Parallel CPU implementations are available in the Scalable Fast Coulomb Solvers (ScaFaCoS), available through the [ScaFaCoS](#) project website and also made available in LAMMPS. However, most modern architectures make the use of accelerators to off-load compute intensive algorithms. Therefore, within this section, we revisit the theoretical foundation to highlight the most important considerations related to GPU implementations of the Ewald Sum and P3M algorithms.

3.1 Ewald Summation Method

The electrostatic energy between two point charges decays with $1/r$. In a system with N point charges, with nominal charges q_i in a cubic periodic three dimensional space with box length L at positions \mathbf{r}_i is given by:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \sum'_{\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}} \frac{q_i q_j}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij} + \mathbf{n}L|}, \quad (6)$$

with $\mathbf{r}_i, j = \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$ and excluding the contribution for $i = j$ for $\mathbf{n} = 0$. This problem is then splitted into short and long range contributions by the identity:

$$\frac{1}{r} = \frac{f(r)}{r} + \frac{1-f(r)}{r}, \quad (7)$$

therefore, giving the possibility of circumventing the slowly decaying long range contribution of the Coulomb potential with the straightforward summation. Here, the first term of the RHS, $f(r)/r$, is a good approximation for the short range contribution to the total energy. The second term $1-f(r)/r$, vary slowly for all values of r , allowing its Fourier transform to be accurately represented by a limited number of \mathbf{k} vectors, where $|\mathbf{k}| < k_{max}$. This enables an efficient calculation of the contribution to the total electrostatic potential in reciprocal space.

Due to the linearity of the field equations, the sums of both aforementioned terms can be performed without significant loss of accuracy. Different contributions can be split into four terms. These can be computed in parallel and are given by:

$$E^{(r)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \sum'_{\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}} q_i q_j \frac{\text{erfc}(\alpha|\mathbf{r}_{ij} + \mathbf{m}L|)}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij} + \mathbf{m}L|}, \quad (8)$$

$$E^{(k)} = \frac{1}{2L^3} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \neq 0} \frac{4\pi}{k^2} e^{-k^2/4\alpha^2} |\tilde{\rho}(\mathbf{k})|^2, \quad (9)$$

$$E^{(s)} = -\frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_i q_i^2, \quad (10)$$

$$E^{(d)} = \frac{2\pi}{(1+2\epsilon')L^3} \left(\sum_i q_i \mathbf{r}_i \right)^2, \quad (11)$$

where, $E^{(r)}$ is the real space contribution, $E^{(k)}$ is the reciprocal space, $E^{(s)}$ is the self-energy, $E^{(d)}$ is the dipole correction and the Fourier transformed density $\tilde{\rho}(\mathbf{k})$ is:

$$\tilde{\rho}(\mathbf{k}) = \int_{V_b} d^3r \rho(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}_j}. \quad (12)$$

The parameter α , here referred as the Ewald parameter, controls the weights between real and reciprocal space contributions, which allows for a tuning of the compute time spent to calculate each contribution. Knowing that the complexity for solving particle-particle interactions in real space and algorithms for Fourier computations have different scaling behaviours, it is possible to find a compromise in parameter choices for the real and reciprocal spaces and splitting parameter leading to the complexity of $O(N^{3/2})$. The possibility to control this splitting parameter became more relevant as modular HPC systems evolved, in which each method can be computed using different resources.

In this context, for a given accuracy, one can choose two parameters among the following set of parameters: real space cutoff, r_{cut} , maximum number of \mathbf{k} modes, k_{max} , and alpha. Having fixed two of them one can optimise the execution

time by properly setting the third one. Therefore, if the implementation supports for calculation of different contributions on several platforms or architectures, one may optimize the use of resources in modern supercomputers. In addition, the parallelization paradigm of GPGPUs allows to calculate per particle k -modes independently on a more efficient manner if compared to CPUs.

3.2 Particle-Particle Particle-Mesh Method

The P3M method maps the system charges onto a mesh, enabling the necessary Fourier transformations to be efficiently performed using a fast Fourier transform (FFT). Simultaneously, the basic free space Coulomb Green's function ($4\pi/k^2$) is modified to ensure that the outcome of the mesh calculation closely approximates the continuum solution. The initial step involves generating a mesh-based charge density, denoted as ρ_M , which is defined at the mesh points (\mathbf{x}_p) given by:

$$\rho_M(\mathbf{r}_p) = \frac{1}{h^3} \int_V d\mathbf{r} W(x_p - x) W(y_p - y) W(z_p - z) \rho(\mathbf{r}), \quad (13)$$

where h represents the mesh spacing. The number of mesh points, N_M , is determined by L/h along each direction, and it is preferable that N_M is a power of two, as this allows the FFT to operate at maximum efficiency. The charge assignment function, W , is categorized by its order, P , which indicates the number of mesh points per coordinate direction over which each charge is distributed. Specifically, W is chosen to be a cardinal B-spline, a piecewise polynomial function with a weight of one. The order P corresponds to the number of sections that comprise the function and its representation in Fourier space is:

$$\tilde{W}(\mathbf{k}) = h^3 \left(\frac{\sin(\frac{1}{2}k_x h)}{\frac{1}{2}k_x h} \frac{\sin(\frac{1}{2}k_y h)}{\frac{1}{2}k_y h} \frac{\sin(\frac{1}{2}k_z h)}{\frac{1}{2}k_z h} \right)^P. \quad (14)$$

Next, we calculate the mesh-based electric field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_p)$ in the second step. The electric field is essentially the derivative of the electrostatic potential. However, there are several methods to implement differentiation on a lattice [14]. For this purpose, we describe the $i\mathbf{k}$ differentiation method, which involves multiplying the Fourier-transformed potential by $i\mathbf{k}$, and has been shown to be the most accurate. Using this approach, the electric field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_p)$ can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_p) = \overleftarrow{\text{FFT}} \left[-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \overrightarrow{\text{FFT}}[\rho_M] \cdot \hat{G}_{\text{opt}} \right] (\mathbf{r}_p), \quad (15)$$

where $\overleftarrow{\text{FFT}}$ and $\overrightarrow{\text{FFT}}$ are the backward and forward FFT respectively, and \hat{G}_{opt} is the modified optimal influence function, derived by Hockney and Eastwood [15] which is written as:

$$\hat{G}_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{k}) \cdot \sum_{\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}^3} \tilde{U}^2(\mathbf{k} + \frac{2\pi}{h}\mathbf{m}) \tilde{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{k} + \frac{2\pi}{h}\mathbf{m})}{|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{k})|^2 \left[\sum_{\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}^3} \tilde{U}^2(\mathbf{k} + \frac{2\pi}{h}\mathbf{m}) \right]^2} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{k}) = -i\mathbf{k} \frac{4\pi}{k^2} e^{-k^2/4\alpha^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{k}) = \tilde{W}(\mathbf{k})/h^3. \quad (17)$$

For the development of the library a generalization of the \hat{G}_{opt} is implemented (see [16] Eq. 30) making it possible to choose from the optimal Green's functions two objective functions for error minimization as target, i.e., Coulomb forces or electrostatic energy.

3.3 Implementation Considerations

All particle and mesh data structures were implemented using the Cabana library [17]. The Cabana library was developed within the Co-Design Center for Particle Applications (CoPA) within the Exascale Computing Project (ECP). Cabana provides particle data structures, algorithms, and communication, as well as structured meshes, mesh algorithms, and particle-mesh interpolation to enable simulations on a variety of platforms including many-core CPU and GPU architectures. Cabana is built on Kokkos, with many additional optional library dependencies, including MPI for multi-node simulation.

The fact that the standard portable model for shared memory parallelism of Cabana is Kokkos, makes it a good choice for intra-node communication model. As described, our study presented in Section 2, Kokkos is suitable for particle based simulations, and the optimized conversion of data structure through the use of so-called *Views* allows for the use of optimal memory access patterns required by different parts of the electrostatics methods.

Algorithms have exploited a particle or mesh based parallelism and can run efficiently on Host and Device architectures using suitable *Memory* and *Execution* Spaces. Since Cabana did not provide support for all methods required for

the implementation of the P3M algorithm, the authors of this Deliverable have extended its functionality and merged the corresponding changes to [Cabana's](#) main branch at GitHub.

The main contributions made were as follows:

- Extension of the highly efficient Fast Fourier Transform for exascale (heFFTe) communication backend support (PR [#799](#));
- Implementation of high order cardinal B-Splines for the particle to mesh and mesh to particle interpolation functions (PR [#800](#)).

4 Electrostatic Solver Library

Implementations of the electrostatic solvers described in the previous section were included into a library to enable application developers in the community to add the ability to compute electrostatic interactions within their custom simulation code. Within this section the interface of the library and the organization of the MPI communication is described.

4.1 Library Interface

The library is inspired by the ScaFaCos library and its interface design is similar to the interface of the previously published library. The current version is still under development and it will be made available to the community soon. Currently the usage of library's Application Program Interface (API) is similar to the following example:

```

1 // create the library data object
2 ExscalicosData<FPT, ExecutionSpace, Kokkos::SharedSpace> data;
3
4 // set the global MPI communicator to be used in the library
5 data.globalComm(comm);
6
7 // set the number of particles in the system
8 data.nSysParticles(nParticles);
9
10 // set the extent of the system
11 data.sysSize(0, systemSize(0));
12 data.sysSize(1, systemSize(1));
13 data.sysSize(2, systemSize(2));
14
15 // create the library object, defining the Kokkos environment and
16 // solver (here: Ewald sum) type using the template parameters
17 Exscalicos<ExscalicosSolver::Ewald, FPT, ExecutionSpace, Kokkos::
18 SharedSpace>
19     e(comm);
20
21 // initialize the object using the data object
22 auto val = e.create(data);
23 // check the correctness of the call
24 val.check();
25
26 // set required parameters, here the range of processes to be used for
27 // the real- and k-space computations of the Ewald solver
28 e.setParameter(ExscalicosEwaldShortRangeProcess(), data, 0, std::min(
29 n ranks - 2, nShortRange - 1));
30 e.setParameter(ExscalicosEwaldLongRangeProcess(), data, std::min(n ranks
31 - 1, nShortRange), n ranks - 1);
32
33 // trigger tuning functions for selected solver
34 val = e.tune(data);
35 val.check();
36
37 // time step loop
38 for (int n = 0; n < nLoop; ++n)
39 {
40     // run the computation on the particles stored in the particle list
41     p1
42     val = e.run(data, p1);
43     val.check();
44 }
45
46 // destroy the library object, triggering necessary deallocations, etc.
47 val = e.destroy(data);
48 val.check();

```

The presented example refers to a system of point charges. However, it can be extended also to higher multipole interactions, e.g., dipoles or quadrupoles.

4.2 MPI Communication management

Both electrostatic solver methods described in Section 3 are based on the idea of splitting the computation of the electrostatic potential and/or force into a real-space and k-space contribution (Equation 7). These computations have different computational complexities.

In order to better utilize the resources provided by state of the art HPC systems, which are mostly based on GPU nodes, which are comprised of GPUs and CPUs, is to split the computation of the real-space and the k-space contributions between resources. A flexible implementation will respect different types of resources, i.e., GPUs, CPUs and their combination, i.e. aiming at a modular implementation, which also allows combination of different HPC resources.

The library will provide a way to facilitate this, by offering the possibility to define a subset of the global communicator provided to the library for each of the contributions (see l. 27 and 28 in the listing above). This work is ongoing at the moment.

In Figure 3 it is shown how the data transfer between the global communicator and the sub-communicators takes place. The global communicator sends the required particle parameters (positions and charges) to each of the sub-communicators, which then compute their respective contributions. The ideal case is that both sub-communicators are independent (cmp. Figure 3), so that this computation can take place in parallel. Afterwards the contributions to potentials and fields are reduced on the global communicator.

Figure 3: Subdivision of the global MPI communicator into sub-communicators to be used for the computation of the real(*r*)- and *k*-space contributions, showing the necessary data transfer between global communicator and each subcommunicator

4.3 Benchmarks

Benchmarks for different problem sizes (16M and 32M particles) were conducted to study i) the scalability of the implementation and ii) the impact of shifting the assignment of resources to the different parts of the Ewald summation solver. In the first benchmark (Figure 4) the resources are split evenly between the two parts of the computation (*r*-space and *k*-space). The benchmarks were conducted on JUWELS booster, which means that four Nvidia A100 GPUs were available per node. Evenly splitting those resources means that for each part two GPUs per node were used. It can be seen that the runtime of the solver is dominated by the time needed for the *k*-space computation for smaller

numbers of nodes used, while for the larger number of nodes used the r -space runtime becomes dominant. Overall a parallel efficiency of $\approx 35\%$ was reached on 128 GPUs (32 nodes).

As a consequence of the finding a larger allocation of resources for the k -space part might be obvious to improve the total run-time. Therefore, the benchmark presented in Figure 5 used three of four GPUs per node for the computation of the k -space contribution and one GPU of each node for the r -space contribution. However, it can be seen that the overall parallel efficiency decays faster than in the first benchmark. This is due to the fact that the r -space computation lost performance and dominates the overall parallel efficiency. The improved scaling behavior of the k -space computation can not be utilized, as the r -space computation always takes longer to execute.

In a third benchmark a larger system was used to investigate the impact of system size on strong scalability. The results are shown in Figure 6. In this benchmark the resources were evenly split between both parts, r - and k -space contributions. It can be seen that an efficiency of $\approx 60\%$ was achieved.

For all benchmarks the different computation parts are executed on sub-communicators which do not share processes. This means that they run independently in parallel but with different individual parallel efficiencies. As a result the sum of both parts is larger than the total runtime. First analysis indicates that this approach of splitting compute resources can be beneficial for node counts where the overall parallel efficiency starts to degrade. In order to be able to better guide the community in that respect further in-depth analysis will be performed.

Figure 4: Strong scaling benchmark of the Ewald summation solver implemented in the library using a system of 16 million randomly placed particles in a periodic system of size 100^3 on Juwels Booster (Forschungszentrum Jülich). The resources are evenly split between the r -space and k -space computation.

Figure 5: Strong scaling benchmark of the Ewald summation solver implemented in the library using a system of 16 million randomly placed particles in a periodic system of size 100^3 on Juwels Booster (Forschungszentrum Jülich). Three of four GPUs are employed for the computation of the k-space contribution, the other GPUs are used for the r-space contribution.

Figure 6: Strong scaling benchmark of the Ewald summation solver implemented in the library using a system of 32 million randomly placed particles in a periodic system of size 126^3 on Juwels Booster (Forschungszentrum Jülich). The resources are evenly split between the r-space and k-space computation.

5 Integration of the ALL load balancing library into LAMMPS

The *A Load balancing Library* (ALL) is a modular, open-source software developed by the Jülich Supercomputing Centre to address the critical challenge of load imbalance in domain-decomposed simulations. In high-performance computing (HPC), particularly in particle-based methods like molecular dynamics or lattice-Boltzmann simulations, spatial domain decomposition is a common strategy to distribute computational workload. However, as simulations evolve, non-uniform distributions of particles or varying local computational costs can lead to significant load imbalances, reducing overall efficiency. ALL provides a suite of dynamic load-balancing strategies specifically designed to redistribute work across processors in such simulations, ensuring better utilization of HPC resources.

By supporting multiple balancing schemes such as histogram and iterative grid partitioning ALL offers flexible and scalable solutions tailored to different application needs. Its integration into widely-used simulation codes like HemeLB and DL_MESO_DPD highlights its effectiveness in improving performance on large-scale systems, including GPU accelerated platforms.

Within the scope of the current Deliverable, we highlight the most efficient and used methods, which are present in the library or being already implemented in LAMMPS:

Tensor Decomposition (Local) This method splits the simulation domain along Cartesian axes using a fixed number of partitions in each direction (e.g., a grid layout). It is an iterative method that, for every dimension, reduces the work over the other dimensions and shifts the borders between two neighbours based on their cumulative work, making it simple but less adaptive to highly uneven load distributions.

- **Classic** For the *classic* approach the work per dimension is collected using the average over the domains in that dimension.
- **Max** The *max* variant considers the maximum work in each of the slices in cartesian direction and considers as objective function an even distribution of the maxima in the slices of each dimension.

Staggered Grid The staggered grid is a special domain decomposition scheme that recursively cuts in each dimension in a defined order. It is a special case of the tiled decomposition as used for recursive bisection and is, in principle, able to produce a perfect decomposition of even load in the system.

- **Global (Global + Histogram)** This method divides the system across domains into grid regions and adjusts the boundaries using global workload histograms. It optimizes the load balance by analyzing the distribution of computational work across the entire domain, then shifts domain boundaries accordingly. It is a global method and uses histogram-based refinement to redistribute work more evenly.
- **Local (Local + Iterative)** Unlike the global variant, this method balances workloads based on local neighbor-to-neighbor interactions. It iteratively adjusts boundaries by exchanging workload data with neighboring domains, gradually improving balance through a series of local updates. This local method uses iteration-based refinement, making it scalable and responsive to localized imbalances.

Recursive Bisection (Global + Iterative) This is a global and hierarchical method that recursively splits the domain into two subregions at each step, aiming to evenly distribute the total workload. The splitting process can be guided by either workload histograms or iterative evaluation of load imbalance. It is effective for complex or non-uniform load distributions but can introduce communication overhead if applied too frequently.

5.1 ALL interface with LAMMPS

ALL balancing methods have been integrated into LAMMPS using the standard definitions of so-called fixes. Once LAMMPS is build with `-D PKG_ALLPKG=yes`, the following options become available:

```
fix ID group-ID balance/all keyword args ...

required keyword/arg pairs

every arg = nevery
  nevery = perform dynamic load balancing every this many steps
grid style args = define grid
  style = staggered or tensor
  staggered args = none
  tensor args = max or classic
    max = use TENSOR_MAX method of ALL
    classic = use TENSOR method of ALL
```

```

weight style args = use weighted particle counts for the balancing
style = group or neigh or time or var or store
group args = Ngroup group1 weight1 group2 weight2 ...
Ngroup = number of groups with assigned weights
group1, group2, ... = group IDs
weight1, weight2, ... = corresponding weight factors
neigh factor = compute weight based on number of neighbors
factor = scaling factor (> 0)
time factor = compute weight based on time spend computing
factor = scaling factor (> 0)
var name = take weight from atom-style variable
name = name of the atom-style variable
store name = store weight in custom atom property defined by fix property/atom
command
name = atom property name (without d_ prefix)

```

At least one of the following keyword/arg pairs is required.
Only one (or none) load balancer is used in a load balancing step.

```

global args = trigger_threshold bin_width
trigger_threshold = float
float = apply load balancer if the imbalance of the load is above this
threshold
bin_width = approximate width of bin (arbitrary positive value)
local args = trigger_threshold (use local balancing)
trigger_threshold = float
float = apply load balancer if the imbalance of the load is above this
threshold

```

optional keyword arg pairs

```

verbose args = none (verbose output to log/screen)
file arg = filename
filename = write stats per rank to filename

```

In addition to the fix balance/all method, a specialized communication style was added in order to correctly and efficiently manage the MPI communicators set by the domain decomposition. Some examples of the available balancing methods are:

```

# histogram method (staggered global), weighted by number of atoms,
# with bin width 0.003, when imbalance >= 1.05
comm_style staggered zyx
fix 5 all balance/all every 1000 grid staggered global 1.05 0.003

```

```

# histogram method (staggered global), weighted by time, with bin width 0.003, when imbalance >= 1.05
comm_style staggered zyx
fix 5 all balance/all every 1000 grid staggered weight time 1.0 global 1.05 0.003

```

```

# staggered local method, weighted by number of atoms, when imbalance >= 1.05
comm_style staggered zyx
fix 5 all balance/all every 100 grid staggered local 1.05

```

```

# tensor method, minimizing average work, weighted by number of atoms, when imbalance >= 1.05
comm_style brick
fix 5 all balance/all every 50 grid tensor classic local 1.05

```

```

# tensor-max method, minimizing maximal work, weighted by number of atoms, when imbalance >= 1.05
comm_style brick
fix 5 all balance/all every 50 grid tensor max local 1.05

```

5.2 General LAMMPS Benchmarks

With the intention to test LAMMPS performance on the most recent architecture present at the EuroHPC latest super-computer JUPITER, we have run several benchmarks of LAMMPS with standard systems. The test consisted in weak and strong scaling on JEDI and JUWELS Booster systems both available at Forschungszentrum Jülich².

For the validation benchmarks, LAMMPS was compiled using GCC 12.3.0, CUDA 12.2, and OpenMPI 4.1.6, and the chosen FFT backend was cuFFT. In Figures 7 and 8 we present the results from porting LAMMPS to the newer architectures.

Figure 7: Single node weak scaling of LAMMPS using JEDI and JUWELS Booster (Forschungszentrum Jülich) for the LJ and Rhodopsin benchmarks in LAMMPS using Kokkos. Scaled LJ simulation containing 55M atoms, and Scaled Rhodopsin simulation containing 16M atoms both with 1 MPI process per GPU. No results are presented for Juwels Booster with 1 and 2 GPUs for the Rhodopsin benchmark due to memory limitation to accommodate the data.

As it can be observed in Figure 7 both systems and architecture combinations show close to ideal scaling within single node configurations. The expected speed up in the newer architecture (2x) is achieved and the larger memory allows for the simulation of bigger system sizes with less computing resources.

In Figure 7b one can observe that due to memory and communication characteristics, it is possible to achieve similar results for the Rhodopsin benchmark using one H100 of the GH200 node instead of three A100 GPUs.

Figure 8: Strong scaling of LAMMPS using JEDI for the LJ and Rhodopsin benchmarks in LAMMPS using Kokkos.

Strong scaling results present in the grouped bars of Figure 8 show that for the LJ benchmark the minimum system size required to profit from allocating multi-node jobs was 55.4 million particles. Once taking into consideration the more complex system, i.e., the Rhodopsin benchmark, one may expect 16.5 million particles to be sufficient at the tested range, which seems to result from the more complex interactions. In fact, the Rhodopsin benchmark includes all electrostatic forces, bonds, dihedrals and improper contributions which results in a much larger computational work compared to the simple LJ case.

²The JEDI system has now been decommissioned and has been integrated into the JUPITER system.

Figure 9: Combined strong and weak scaling of LAMMPS at the pre-exascale supercomputer JEDI (Forschungszentrum Jülich). Solid bars use the staggered global load balancing method from the ALL library integrated into LAMMPS and hatched bars use the recursive bisection load balancing method native to LAMMPS.

5.3 Benchmark with balancing methods

For testing the performance of the load balancing library, a synthetic benchmark was generated removing atoms from a spherical region at the centre of the LJ standard benchmark. The system was scaled in the same manner as the ones presented in the previous section.

In Figure 9 results show comparisons between load balancing methods, i.e., RCB, which is one of LAMMPS's native benchmark methods, and the staggered global methods (ALL) using the same interval for checking the load imbalance and activating the load balancing procedure with a common criterion. The balancing commands added to the input script were:

```
comm_style staggered zyx
fix 5 all balance/all every 50 grid staggered global 0.9 0.003
```

in the case of using the method available through the integration with ALL, and :

```
comm_style tiled
fix 5 all balance 50 rcb 0.9
```

for LAMMPS's recursive bisection algorithm (RCB).

It can be observed that for all numbers of nodes the staggered/global method (solid bars) resulted in a performance improvement of 30% to 50% compared to RCB (hatched bars), which shows a promising capability of enhancing the performance of load imbalanced simulations on exascale supercomputers.

These simulations were performed using the GPU package in LAMMPS through the use of `-sf gpu` command line.

6 Conclusion and Perspectives

This deliverable presents the developments achieved through the efforts of Task 2.3. Sections 2 to 5 cover performance portability, electrostatic methods and implementation considerations, library API and benchmarks, and the integration of the ALL load balancing library into LAMMPS. These individual topics are interconnected, with portability aspects influencing the design choices of electrostatic solvers and their impact on target systems for optimal load balancing methods that interface with particle simulations.

Kokkos has proven to be a reliable choice for porting codes to newer architectures, offering significant advantages in complex data structures and widespread community adoption. Although it may not yield the best overall $\bar{\Phi}$ values, it consistently performs well on systems with a robust backend software stack. As demonstrated in Section 2, Kokkos matches the performance of native/vendor-recommended platform-dependent solutions without requiring laborious compiler optimizations. However, it is essential to note that platform-related compiler optimizations may positively impact Kokkos' performance, and system maintainers are encouraged to explore this topic.

Section 3 presents algorithmic considerations aimed at extracting the desired performance from modern exascale architectures. Each independent step can utilize specific sub-communicators and run in parallel on CPU+GPU combinations or across modular partitions. Both Ewald summation and P3M methods employ either particle or mesh-based parallelism through Cabana methods or Kokkos Multi-Dimensional Range loops.

The tentative API of the library and preliminary benchmarks are presented in Section 4. These benchmarks validate and highlight the library's modular capability, demonstrating the splitting of r and k -space methods and their respective scalabilities for the Ewald summation method (Figures 4 to 6). These benchmarks were performed by using two independent allocations for the r - and k -space parts on Juwels Booster (Forschungszentrum Jülich). The discussion includes a critical assessment of the requirements and capabilities of a balancing method to run r - and k -space parts most efficiently. Strong scaling of 16 and 32 million particles scaled from 4 to 128 GPUs reveals that parallel efficiency is affected by the manner in which computational effort of r - and k -space parts is distributed onto resources. Initial analysis suggests that this approach to resource allocation can be beneficial for node counts where overall parallel efficiency begins to degrade. Further in-depth analysis will be conducted to provide more comprehensive guidance.

The P3M implementation is currently undergoing validation, and its extraction to the new electrostatic library has commenced. We plan to analyze the impact of modular allocation with mesh methods using the same methodology presented for the Ewald Summation. Both methods will be optimized for running on Europe's largest supercomputer, [JUPITER](#).

Lastly, the LAMMPS porting to the newest architecture has exhibited expected weak and strong scaling behavior. Performance on GH200 nodes is expected to be twice as fast as on the previous Nvidia GPU architecture (A100). For very large simulations, energy efficiency improves more than twofold, as fewer nodes and GPUs are required to perform equally sized simulations.

Following the analysis of LAMMPS scaling behavior on both JEDI and Juwels Booster, preliminary results using the integration of ALL into LAMMPS are presented in Section 5.3. As the performance of load balancing depends on initial configuration and computing costs (described in Section 5.2), a more comprehensive study will be conducted to evaluate the differences between LAMMPS' implemented balance methods and those added by the integration with the ALL library. The standardization of the interface is near to completion and will be made available to the community by creating a pull request to LAMMPS' main repository.

Acknowledgements

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Acronyms used

HPC High Performance Computing
FFT fast Fourier transform
EuroHPC European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
GPU Graphical Processing Unit
MD Molecular Dynamics
GCS Gauss Supercomputing Centre
API Application Program Interface

Software mentioned

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture
heFFTe highly efficient Fast Fourier Transform for exascale
ALL A Load balancing Library
ScaFaCoS Scalable Fast Coulomb Solvers

URLs referenced

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